

Review

Institutional Pressures and Supply Chain Finance Solutions Among Smallholder Farmers: The Moderating Role of Financial and Technology Literacy

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Abstract: Institutional pressures, encompassing normative, coercive, and mimetic influences, significantly impact smallholder farmers' ability to access supply chain finance (SCF) solutions in Burundi. This research, grounded in institutional theory, employed a comprehensive methodology involving structured questionnaires distributed both online and in-person, achieving 230 responses. The study utilized a correlational matrix and hierarchical regression analysis to evaluate the interplay between institutional pressures, financial literacy, and technological access on SCF adoption.

The findings indicate that financial literacy enhances the likelihood of SCF adoption, with technologically literate farmers and firms better equipped to leverage SCF opportunities. Moderation analysis revealed a positive interaction between access to information technology and institutional pressures, enhancing SCF utilization. Furthermore, the study highlighted the critical role of SCF in improving operational and financial performance, particularly through solutions like mobile money credit and microcredit. Key recommendations include fostering multi-stakeholder collaboration to establish supportive norms and regulations for SCF implementation.

This research provides actionable insights for policymakers and practitioners, emphasizing the importance of financial education and digital literacy to bolster the agricultural sector's resilience and efficiency. The study underscores SCF's potential to transform agricultural productivity and mitigate the financial constraints faced by Burundi's smallholder farmers.

Keywords: Supply chain finance, institutional pressure, financial literacy, technological access, smallholder farmers, Burundi, agricultural finance

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Introduction

Smallholder farmers in Burundi face substantial challenges stemming from financial constraints, technological limitations, and the external pressures of regulatory, market-driven, and social demands. Institutional theory provides

a valuable lens for understanding these challenges, positing that normative, coercive, and mimetic pressures shape organizations' responses to their external environment. Despite the abundance of natural resources and agricultural potential in Burundi, the sector's contribution remains undermined by limited access to financial solutions and technology. This gap has dire consequences, with over 50% of children malnourished and farmers constituting the majority of those living in poverty (FAO, 2015).

Supply Chain Finance (SCF) emerges as a pivotal solution to alleviate these challenges by addressing the financing gaps faced by smallholder farmers. SCF gained prominence in the wake of the 2008 global financial crisis, emphasizing its relevance to fostering financial inclusion and economic stability (Klapper & Randall, 2011; Wuttke et al., 2013). While SCF practices are well-established in developed economies, their adoption in the agricultural sector of developing nations like Burundi remains nascent and under-researched. Recent studies (e.g., Stewart, 2020) underscore the pressing need to explore how institutional forces influence SCF adoption among smallholder farmers. This study contributes to the growing body of SCF literature by investigating the role of institutional pressures in driving SCF adoption among smallholder farmers in Burundi. Specifically, it examines how financial literacy and technological access moderate the relationship between institutional pressures and SCF solutions. The hypotheses are as follows:

- **H1:** There is a positive relationship between institutional pressures and SCF solutions.
- **H2:** The relationship between institutional pressures and SCF solutions will be moderated by smallholder farmers' access to technology and information.
- **H3:** The relationship between drivers and SCF solutions will be moderated by smallholder farmers' financial knowledge.
- **H4:** The smallholder farmer performance will be positively related to the supply chain finance solutions.

By addressing these hypotheses, the study aims to provide actionable insights for stakeholders, including policymakers, financial institutions, and agricultural practitioners, to design targeted interventions that enhance SCF adoption and its impact on agricultural productivity in Burundi.

Literature review

Institutionary theory

Institutional theory is frequently used to explain the external factors that compel a business to initiate or adopt a new practice (Saeed et al., 2018). According to institutional theory, acting under the standards and expectations of the institutional context significantly improves an organization's chances of survival (Meyer & Rowan, 1977). The theory proposed three pressures, which are the normative, mimetic, and coercive pressures (Kapadia, 2019).

Normative pressures are social pressures placed on organizations and their members to conform to certain norms (Meyer, & Rowan, 1977). DiMaggio and Powell (1983) proposed that normative pressures are generated by various groups associated with professionalization, such as educational institutions promoting cognitive behavior, professionals from industry groups and associations, or nongovernmental organizations with an interest in a specific industry. However, a growing body of empirical evidence suggests that clients are a key component of these pressures because they have a direct or indirect interest in the organization (Saeed et al., 2018).

Coercive pressures are a collection of formal and informal pressures applied to an organization by other organizations on which it is dependent, as well as cultural and societal expectations (Davidsson, et al., 2006). Coercive pressure is exerted by external stakeholders like government authorities and non-governmental organizations. These types of pressures are frequently associated with formal institutions such as regulations or laws, but they can also be informal expectations placed on organizations. According to Li (2014), new political and legislative rules are more likely to enforce organizational change; for example, the implementation of new environmental regulations frequently forces

organizations to innovate. The African smallholder farmers have however been let down by governments as efforts to support this sector most of the time fail to meet the needs and demands (Marak & Pillai, 2019).

Mimetic pressure arises when companies engage in a competition seeking superior performance (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Mimetic pressures are demands for organizations to imitate other organizations to deal with uncertainty. Meyer and Rowan (1977), writing a few years before DiMaggio and Powell, observed that nothing beats the repetition of behaviors that have previously been perceived as efficient by the market, companies responding to mimetic pressures can obtain economic benefits by being more competitive. Mimetic pressures are thus expected to produce effective solutions at a lower cost (Messy & Atkinson, 2013).

SCF Solutions

Many small farmers run their businesses informally, and they frequently lack the records and financial information that banks require to lend. The opportunities offered by SCF solutions are more precisely influenced by the context and the economic model as well as by the respective roles played by all participants within the chain (Smith & Buttress, 2005). The lack of financial institutions branches in rural areas makes it even harder; the smallholder farmers are greatly underserved and overlooked (Ruiz, 2014). SCF solutions that can help them need to be tailored to their needs and since financial institutions are unwilling to do that due to high costs, new technologies can be leveraged to access the capital they seriously need (Xu et al., 2018).

Institutional forces such as regulatory (coercive), market (normative), and competitive (mimetic) are driving small agricultural businesses to think beyond the traditional financing channels (Juárez-Luis, 2018). The SCF solution creates new financing opportunities for agriculture, improves returns and repayments of finance, and strengthens links between chain participants.

In this study, the authors focused on four key SCF solutions; mobile money loans (mobile money), micro-credit, account payables and receivables. Mobile money has been hailed as a game-changing tool for increasing access to financial services in low-resource settings (Simon & Anderson-Manjang, 2021). Besides, digital money makes up the majority of mobile money flow and more value is circulating in the money system than existing (Manjang et al., 2021).

Secondly, micro-credit support to smallholder farmers bridges the financing gap for many local farmers. In this situation, farmers received credits either in cash or in kind to support their agricultural activities. These loans are usually secured in groups where the group members act as collateral to each other. Also, accounts payable to suppliers are usually rollover to the farmers for them re-invest in their farming activities which serve as a source of funds for them (Smith & Buddress, 2005). Sometimes such monies have little interest in the principal amount. Lastly, accounts receivable are the goods or services the smallholder farmers arrange for on a credit or defer-payment basis. While the accounts receivable are deferred costs to the suppliers or companies, it provides relief and a source of funds for the farmers to focus on their agricultural products (Pagell, 2004).

Financial knowledge

Awareness and access to financial services are critical to agricultural development as it increases income through productive investment, create employment opportunities, facilitate investments in other sectors of production (Akinlo, 2014). Some researchers believe financial inclusion can be achieved through financial literacy or education. Financial literacy is defined as having the knowledge, skills, and confidence to manage one's finances effectively while taking one's economic and social circumstances into account (Délèze, 2018). According to Kapadia (2019). Financial knowledge

can help people budget their finances properly, participate in savings, look for better interest rates on debt, and ensure proper record keeping. People who practice financial discipline can fully understand their cash inflows and outflows. According to Atkinson and Messy (2013), low levels of financial inclusion are linked to lower levels of financial literacy, and policymakers should establish financial literacy and education policies to help enhance the level of financial inclusion (Messy & Atkinson, 2013). The situation is further exacerbated in the least developed countries (LDCs), where more than 90% of the population lacks access to the formal financial system. Limited literacy, especially financial literacy (basic mathematics, business finance skills, and a lack of understanding), frequently limits demand for financial services. For many farmers, the decision to grow in season, invest in more efficient farming methods, or purchase new equipment depends on their access to finance (Ravikumar, 2017)

Access to technology

Agricultural research is becoming progressively private, with an emphasis on knowledge-intensive technologies being developed for larger, commercial farms (Luc et al., 2011). However, local farmers lack access to technological information. Local farmers are mostly familiar with informal and other traditional sources of access to credit (Ramasamy, 2020). The technological barrier has resulted in unknown access, efficiency, and affordability of SCF (Heugens & Lander, 2009).

Meanwhile, Gelsomino et al (2016) argued that technology is providing a way to better this situation by providing access to a variety of information to help them decide when to buy inputs or sell their yields, saving them time and money; plan for weather changes that will allow them to capitalize on rain or protect plants from frost; choose the highest-yielding seed varieties, as well as distinguish between disease and pests and respond accordingly. Research carried out in Kenya found that technology literacy, particularly mobile phones, can improve the speed with which farmers in rural areas obtain, exchange, and manipulate information (Muriithi, Brett, & Ogaleh, 2009).

Conceptual Framework

The researcher deduced from the supply chain finance, institutional theory, and agricultural firm performance literature and proposed a model. The framework deeply analyzes the relationship among institutional pressures, financial solutions and firm performance. Again, the study moderated the relationship using financial knowledge, access to information, and technology. First, the study assumed that drivers such as institutional drivers (normative, mimetic, and coercive) and capital shortage trigger supply chain financing solutions. In the model, the researcher explicitly divided the firm performance into financial and operational performance for a better understanding of the outcome. The study model contributes to SCF because it overrides the straightforward concepts of factor-performance research by past scholars. The whole idea is presented in figure 1

Figure 1: A research framework Based on the study framework in figure 1, the study proposed the following hypothesis;

H1: There is a positive relationship between institutional pressures and SCF solutions

H2: The relationship between institutional pressures and SCF solutions will be moderated by smallholder farmers' access to technology and information.

H3: The relationship between drivers and SCF solutions will be moderated by smallholder farmers' financial knowledge

H4: The smallholder farmer performance will be positively related to the supply chain finance solutions.

Developing Measurement Constructs

The study designs the measurement of constructs for each factor in the model through rigorous processes. Initially, the study followed the definitions of Edward and Bagozzi (2000). They defined a construct as a conceptual term for a phenomenon of theoretical interest. The causative factors under the model are the institutional pressures (normative, mimetic, and coercive), and SCF solution (micro-credit, mobile money, accounts payable and accounts receivable). This study defined normative pressure as the farmers' association and current market structure encouraging suppliers to implement SCF. In this case, SCF practices in the agriculture industry are becoming the norm (Wang et al., 2018; Colwell et al., 2013).

Secondly, on mimetic pressure, the study related it to farmers associations increasing their financial performance through SCF practices by comparing with other local farmers in the community (Badar et al., 2020; Daddi et al., 2016). Coercive pressure was defined as the rules and regulations that are pushing the implementation of SCF. A self-response financial performance relates to formal records of the financial operations or activities and position of the agricultural business or entity. However, since most small agriculture firms or businesses do not keep proper financial records of their business, the study adopted the CAMEL rating approach (capital adequacy, asset, management capability, earnings, and liquidity).

Moreover, the third section presents measures of institutional pressures under three major themes; coercive pressure, mimetic pressure, and normative. The study measured institutional pressure questions using a five-point Likert Scale of "strongly disagree, disagree, uncertain, agree, and strongly agree".

Methodology

This research employs a cross-sectional survey to gather information from farmers across Burundi. The authors used a stratified sampling technique where elements of the population were put into strata. Using the stratified approach, the researcher grouped the agricultural activities into crop farming, fish farming, mixed farmers, and animal/livestock farming. From the four strata mentioned, the study selected two hundred and thirty (230) crop and tree farmers, fish farmers, animal/livestock farmers, and mixed farmers.

The study used closed-ended questionnaires to collect information from the respondents. The questionnaires were designed to cover all the research objectives. The authors employed several approaches in the administration of the questionnaire. The researcher considers the time relevant, convenience, and educational factors and applies the appropriate method accordingly.

Firms or individuals who have smartphones and can read were allowed to scan the link of the questions and answer online. Besides, the study adopted the delivery and collection (drop and pick later), especially when the respondent can fill out the questionnaires personally. This means the questionnaires were given to participants and the researcher

picked them later. However, against the background that the educational levels of the majority of farm owners were very low, face-to-face interactions were necessary to complete the questionnaires.

Moreover, the researcher also employed telephone conservation on farmers who agreed to participate in the survey. In this case, the author sought the consent of the farmers and write down their mobile numbers for the questionnaire to be conducted via the telephone. After one month, the researchers collected the desired data for the study.

Results and Discussion

The study examines the participants' background such as age, gender, years in service, role, sales volume, etc.

Table 1 Participant biodata

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	143	62.2
Female	87	37.8
Total	230	100.0
Age		
below 25 years	8	3.5
26-30 years	69	30.0
31-35 years	51	22.2
36-40 years	33	14.3
41-45 years	64	27.8
46-60 years	5	2.2
Total	230	100.0
Years working		
less than 5	59	25.7
5-10 years	101	43.9
11-15 years	56	24.3
more than 15 years	14	6.1
Total	230	100.0
Role		
Owner	162	70.4
owner's relative	5	2.2
member owner	49	21.3
human resource	7	3.0
administrative officer	7	3.0
Total	230	100.0

In terms of gender perspective, 143(62.2%) are males and 87(37.8%) are females. The researcher is not interested in gender bias and the difference has no statistical influence on the analytical outcome. The respondents' feedback indicated that 69(30.0%) of them are between the ages of 26 to 30, 64(27.8) are between 41 to 50 years, 51(22.2%) are between 31 to 35 years, 33(14.3%) respondents are between 36 to 40 years, 8(3.5%) are below 25 years and 5(2.2%) are between 46 to 60 years. The age information shows that smallholder farmers are largely within 26-30 years, which means the Burundi agriculture sector has an active and better outlook labor force that could sustain future innovation in the country.

Numbers of years at work have been used to measure experience by many researchers.

Similarly, this research discovered that out of the total respondents 101, which represents 43.9% had worked between 5-10 years. Besides, 59(25.7%) have less than 5 years of working experience, 56(24.3%) have working experience between 11 to 15 years and 14(6.1%) of them have worked over 15 years in which 162(70.4%) are owners, 49(21.3%) are members of owners, 7(3.3%) are human resources, 7(3.3%) are administrator officers and 5(2.2%) are related to owners.

Famers’ activities and background

Table 2 exhibits smallholders’ farmers and firm-related biodata from the respondents. The study observed that 178(77.4%) said their work was on family farms and family farmlands (i.e. owned by the family). Moreover, 37(16.1%) work in foreign or joint ventures. Additionally, 15(6.5%) work in state-owned institutions or government-sponsored farms. Interestingly, the majority earn their income from commerce, which translates to 79(34.3%), whereas those from business activities were 44(19.1%). Other participants argued that they get income from their salaries and 40 (17.4%). The research enquired about the farmers' or firms' average annual sales volume in the last five years. Annually, 82(35.7%) respondents said they harvest between 100,000 to 200,000 volume of their cultivated products, 64(27.8%) harvest 50,000 to 100,000 volume, 50 (21.7%) harvest more than 200,000 and only 34(14.8%) harvest less than 50,000 volumes. Concerning their accessibility to the market, 222(96.5%) said they get access to the local market, 7(3.0%) use middlemen and only 1(0.4%) get access to the urban market. Finally, 70(30.4%) said they harvest 2 times within a year, 55(23.9%) harvest more than 3 times within a year 53(23.0%) harvest twice a years, and 52(22.6%) harvest once a year.

Table 2 Smallholders farmers and firm-related biodata

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mode
Ownership nature			
family farm	178	77.4	Family farm
state-owned	15	6.5	
the foreign or joint venture	37	16.1	
Source of income			
Salary	44	19.1	Commerce
business activity	67	29.1	
Commerce	79	34.3	
Others	40	17.4	
Total	230	100.0	
Annual sales volume			
less than 50, 000	34	14.8	100k-200k
50, 000 - 100, 000	64	27.8	
100,000-200, 000	82	35.7	
more than 200, 000	50	21.7	
Total	230	100.0	
Access to market			
local market	222	96.5	local
urban market	1	.4	
use of middlemen	7	3.0	
Total	230	100.0	

number of harvests in a year			
1	52	22.6	
2	70	30.4	2
3	53	23.0	
more than 3	55	23.9	
Total	230	100.0	

Correlation analysis of drivers and SCF practices

The research examines the effects of SCF drivers and SCF solutions. The drivers were measured using normative pressure, mimetic pressure, and coercive pressure. First, the authors used a statistical package for social scientists (SPSS) to test for reliability. The overall Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient was 0.835, which is greater than the threshold of 0.70.

Table 3 illustrates the correlational matrix among the study variables. It shows the direction of association as well as the strength among these variables.

Table 3 Correlational matrix among study variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Firm performance	1						
CP	-.233**	1					
NP	-.231**	.260**	1				
MP	-.443**	.200**	.636**	1			
Microcredit	.240**	.024	.453**	.668**	1		
Mobile money	-.075	.094	.404**	.538**	.532**	1	
Account receivable	.361**	.231**	.244**	.354**	.151*	.140*	1
Account payable	.333**	.159*	.121	.230**	.020	-.009	.946**

Note; total respondents = 230, **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed), CP = coercive pressure, NP = normative pressure, MP = mimetic pressure

(a) Coercive pressure

Similarly, the research aimed to investigate the influence of coercive pressure on SCF solutions in this study. First, the study reported no statistical association between coercive pressure and microcredit ($r = 0.024, p > 0.01$), and mobile money ($r = 0.094, p > 0.01$). This means that the first two hypotheses were rejected on the other hand. The study supported the assumption that there is a positive and significant relationship between coercive pressure and accounts receivable and account payable ($r = 0.159^{**}, p < 0.05$).

H4a: coercive pressure leads to access to micro-credit.	<i>Rejected</i>
H4b: coercive pressure lead to access to mobile money	<i>Rejected</i>
H4c: coercive pressure lead to the access of account receivable	<i>Accepted</i>
H4d: coercive pressure lead to the access of account payable	<i>Accepted</i>

(b) Normative pressure

Accepting professional guidelines in the field of agriculture has some impact on smallholder farmers. For instance, this study indicated a strong positive and significant association between normative pressure and microcredit financing ($r = 0.453^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Besides, normative pressure and mobile money correlated positively ($r = 0.404^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). In the same way, the researcher observed a significant and positive correlation between normative pressure and account receivable ($r = 0.244^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). However, there was no linkage between normative pressure and account payable.

H2a: Normative pressure leads to access of micro-credit	<i>Accepted</i>
H2b: Normative pressure leads to access to mobile money.	<i>Accepted</i>
H2c: Normative pressure leads to access to account receivable	<i>Accepted</i>
H2d: Normative pressure leads to the access of account payable.	<i>Rejected</i>

(c) Mimetic pressure

The study found evidence to support a positive and strong association between competitive (mimetic pressure) and microcredit ($r = 0.668^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). This means competition among smallholder farmers influences the likelihood to access microcredit in the country. Moreover, the study revealed that mimetic pressure and mobile money are significantly associated ($r = 0.532^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, account receivable and account payable all correlated positively with mimetic pressure with correlation coefficient ($r = 0.354^{**}$, $p < 0.01$) and ($r = 0.230^{**}$, $p < 0.01$) respectively.

H3a: Mimetic pressure leads to access of micro-credit	<i>Accepted</i>
H3b: Mimetic pressure leads to access to mobile money	<i>Accepted</i>
H3c: Mimetic pressure leads to access to account receivable	<i>Accepted</i>
H3d: Mimetic pressure leads to the access of account payable	<i>Accepted</i>

Hierarchical regression analysis

To buttress the correlation and descriptive statistics, the researcher used hierarchical regression to examine the contribution of the independent and moderator variables to the overall model. The study used the enter method and tested the independent factors on the dependent variable in the model in three steps.

In step 1 of the model, the overall variability of the SCF solution was 42.5%, whereas the correlational effect was $r = .652$. The model was statistically significant, $F(3, 226) = 55.68$. Here, only the mimetic variable had a significant and positive relationship with the SCF solution (Step 1: $\beta = 0.616$, $p < 0.05$). Both coercive and normative variables were insignificant with SCF solutions.

In step 2 of the model, the researcher entered financial knowledge to moderate the independent factors. The interaction term increased the model's overall variability to 51.1% ($R^2 = 0.511$). The presence of financial knowledge contributed 8.6% ($\Delta R^2 = 0.086$) to SCF solution explanation power. The model was statistically significant, $F(1, 228) = 58.87$, whereas the financial knowledge coefficient was (Step 2: $\beta = 0.179^{**}$, $p < 0.005$). This means that access to financial knowledge is relevant to smallholder farmers and their agricultural firms in Burundi to understand and access credit from the financial market to improve their financial and operational performance.

The researcher tested access to information and technology in step 3 of the model. The overall r-squared change is just 0.5, which is less than 1%. The information and technology coefficient was not recognized in the model. Lastly, the R-squared did not change in any ($.511 - .516 = 0.005$). The study attached that access to information and technology is vital to agricultural firms' performance but not access to SCF solutions such as mobile money, microcredit, and account receivable, and payable.

Table 4 Hierarchical regression analysis for analysis

Variables	Financial knowledge, information, and technology		
	Step 1	Step2	Step 3
<i>Main factors</i>			
Mimetic	.616**	.510**	.490**
Coercive	.049	.079	.091
Normative	.044	-.021	-.020
<i>Interaction term</i>			
Financial knowledge		.179**	.490**
Information & technology			.123
R	.652 ^a	.715 ^b	.719 ^c
R ²	.425*	.511*	.516
F	55.68*	58.87*	47.83*
ΔR ²	.425	.086	.005

N = 230, 2-tailed test. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, dependent factor = SCF solutions

Implication and Conclusion

Theoretical implication

This study draws references from the institutional theory as a motivation behind SCF practices among smallholder farmers and agricultural firms in Burundi. Known widely, the institutional theory asserted that the institutional environment can strongly influence the development of formal structures in firms. At the individual level (smallholder farmers), the market pressure and the need for innovation and performance interplay for persons to adopt SCF practices. Institutional theory suggests companies’ social, environmental, and economic performances are greatly affected by the institutional environment in which a company operates. The theoretical framework assumes that organizations are embedded in a web of values, norms, rules and beliefs that guide their behavior and practices (Badar et al., 2020). Firms or individuals react to institutional pressure (coercive, mimetic, and normative) to stay relevant in the industry. These pressures enable firms or smallholder farmers to access SCF solutions. For instance, government regulation.

Coercive pressure is exerted by external stakeholders like government authorities and non-governmental organizations, and this forces agriculture firms and farmers to implement SCF solutions, which in turn promote the firm financial and operational performance. Coercive pressure deals with multifactor difficulties such as the internal behavior of the firm and individual farmers (Roxas and Coetzer, 2012). Coercive pressures are positively related to the implementation level of SCF and turn out to have the strongest influence on promoting the implementation of SCF. The positive effect of mimetic pressures on the implementation of SCF provides useful insights into managerial decision-making. For example, SCF is an innovative financial solution, many uncontrollable factors, such as political, economic, social, and technological factors, as the differences in cultures, rules, regulations, and tax frameworks from one country to another, make it difficult for trade partners from different counties to implement SCF.

Mimetic pressure arises when firms or companies engage in a competition seeking superior performance (Latan et al., 2018). SFC solution adoption can be costly but beneficial. Companies need to respond to their competitors’ actions and behaviors. Agricultural firms and individuals are moved to access SCF solutions because of competitive pressure from

rival firms. In Latan et al. (2018), they asserted that normative pressure comes from suppliers, customers, associations like companies' trade unions, the media, and other social entities. Trade unions and other associations are usually considered the basic entities that create normative pressures. These pressures force farmers, and agricultural firms to explore opportunities in the financial markets. Researchers (Berthod, 2016) revealed that research on the enablers of SCF has mainly been focused on economic rationality and efficiency mechanisms, while research on the effects of institutional pressures on the SCF. Given that the implementation of SCF practices is increasingly gaining attention in both practice and academia (Xu, 2018; Gels, 2016), the current study indicates that institutional theory is a promising paradigm for SCF research in the agriculture sector.

Policy implication

Based on the study's theoretical and policy implications, the study provides the following recommendations:

- a) Managers from state-owned firms should pay attention to emulating successful SCF practices in the field to reduce uncertainty and risk. Also, individuals and private firms should conform to industrial practices and be smarter in competition to take the first-mover advantage.
- b) To promote the diffusion of SCF practices and provide effective guidelines for SCF implementation, relevant stakeholders, such as the government, professional associations, and trade bodies, should work together to focus on establishing and improving shared norms and regulations related to the implementation of SCF. The positive response of policymakers and industry associations to external institutional pressures can enable firms to implement SCF better and benefit from it. This can be in the form of agricultural cooperation to access the financial market.

Given the lack of policy support, relevant professionals, and the imperfect governance mechanism in the current SCF practices in Burundi, stakeholders should establish and improve relevant laws and regulations and improve the credit rating evaluation system to provide a superior institutional environment for agricultural firms' and smallholder farmers to access SCF solution.

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